

School-Related Stress Among Teenagers in Pakistan: What Studies Say

Created by Hamdan Zakir Khan
Eden College
mhamdankhan248@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of the research is to investigate whether academics, social and economic factors are responsible for stress among teenagers in Pakistan, and to what extent is the stress level among teenagers in schools and colleges. Furthermore, the research analyses the studies of different authors and gives their conclusion with similarities between the studies. The research also investigates the condition of the education system in Pakistan and the future goals of students who wish to go abroad for further studies. It was concluded that most of these students face stress due to overload of homework and assignments and to make things more stressful, they have to prepare for exams which are a crucial requirement for further studies. Students are advised to maintain a schedule through which they can balance the amount of work everyday, as well as take part in counselling sessions that help to reduce stress and create a healthy and optimistic environment.

Introduction

Stress is what most students call the reason behind their delay in preparation for exams or the lack of focus in studies, but some claim it as a source of fuel for the energy they need to push themselves hard so they can achieve success. This is common among Pakistani teenagers, who are basically new generation students that have higher education dreams, especially when many of them want to pursue their studies abroad. Some would return to do something for the country, while others would prefer to live abroad. This is due to “brain drain” that is common in Pakistan and what is causing most of our new generation to find careers abroad. The economic and social factors play an important role in shaping the condition of Pakistan that also affects the education system. Not only is it mandatory to have proper education, students must also be taught to manage stress and time so they have no issues regarding academics.

Literature Review

- **Academic Pressure and Future Goals**

In today's world, it is common for teenagers to suffer academic stress and worry about their future goals. According to Journal of Research and Reflections (2014), stress is a condition of tension (mental or physical or both) which results in emotional loss and pain, according to the dictionary of psychology (Lai, Chao, Chang and Chang, 1996). On the other hand, the Journal of Development and Social Sciences states that a large percentage of students who are preparing to start college are looking forward to the experience. This means the large percentage will most likely suffer stress and mental or physical problems that will become a burden in their future goals. This large percentage of students wish to pursue their goals, yet they already are on the verge of failure. This is becoming more common as political and economic situations in Pakistan are also responsible for the deteriorating academic performance of students, especially teenagers, who expressed anger regarding the ongoing situation and wish to go abroad to fulfill their dreams. Many, if not all, want to get good grades to please their parents. Some find it hard to adapt to the different characteristics of the environment they are studying in. Hence, many who are even unaware of the situation, will most likely suffer stress due to lack of academic performance. Another example is when students are told to study so they can fulfill their parents' wish to become a doctor, engineer etc. They struggle hard in order to pursue that desire, for which they are to face stress in the form of hardships.

- **Psychological and Behavioral Effects**

According to Journal of Asian Development Studies (2023), both male and female adolescents are susceptible to behavioural and psychological issues. Poor physical, mental, and behavioural health can negatively affect their academic performance, meaning their future goals are threatened and it is most likely that they will lose interest in academics, and likely focus on non-academics that will divert them from their future goals. Many wish to study abroad because they think they will not get any suitable job in Pakistan, even if they complete their education from a national university. "After getting higher education and passing certain exams, they got jobs in the USA and only a few of them returned to the country", says a study from the Journal of Research and Reflections (2014). Overall, the mental stress level in teenagers was underestimated, as teenagers pose higher risk to poor behavior that may affect their studies due to low tolerance against stress. Most, who will complete their education from abroad in future, will think of the ongoing situation in Pakistan and decide to apply for a job abroad instead of doing something for their country. Teenagers argued that daily homework and assignments are causing them stress and panic, therefore they find academics too hard and exams too tough to pass, such that most teenagers will be pleased if they only get passed in exams rather than failing and

retrying. This is now common in every school of Pakistan. Some even ditch school or college so they can prepare from home to avoid being part of the stress and become consistent in their studies.

- **Perceptions, Coping Strategies, and Thomas Theorem**

The Thomas Theorem, proposed by William Isaac Thomas in 1928, is a sociological theory within the Symbolic Interaction Paradigm. It suggests that circumstances have actual consequences if they are perceived as accurate (Journal of Asian Development Studies, 2023). This explains that the stress level among students has actual consequences, especially brain drain and lack of interest in studies, because they are too tough to make them stressed. On the contrary, The 2006 Kranz study showed that students perceived stress as ordinary to above average, with a mean score of 3.8 out of 5, and that 70.5 percent of the students reported using an active strategy to cope with stress, such as exercising, playing basketball, or swimming (Journal of Development and Social Sciences, 2023). However, this study relied on self-reported data which may lack reliability. This also shows that non-academics can play a part in controlling the stress and anxieties of students, especially teenagers who can learn or develop new skills. Though it is not right to assume that non-academics can always cure your stress problem. For not too many, they rely on time management so they cannot be stressed about work, especially when some teenagers do part-time jobs, whether online or physically to fulfill their needs. According to Journal of Development and Social Sciences (2023), female students take more academic stress than male students, and both of them have high levels of physical and social stress. Both are advised to attend counselling sessions that teach how to control stress and live a healthy and peaceful life.

Methodological Notes from Reviewed Studies

The Journal of Development and Social Sciences (2023) obtained data from a self-developed questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale for getting relevant and correct data from respondents. The content of the questionnaire was selected keeping in mind the research objectives of the study. They asked the students about physical, academic and social factors regarding stress. In another approach described in the Journal of Asian Development Studies (2013), it was necessary to understand how participants, mainly teenagers, interpret their experiences. However, this research was only conducted in Rawalpindi due to time and budget constraints, so its results cannot be applied everywhere. On the other hand, questionnaire items were approved by the education research department and further survey and pilot study was conducted to ensure validity of the research. Both researches concluded that stress affects people in

different ways, either experience or factors related to stress. In both cases, stress was caused due to external factors including academics.

Social and Economic Factors

According to Journal of Research and Reflections (2014), brain drain is the main cause of people migrating from Pakistan, due to which over 36,000 people went abroad for professions. This connects with the idea of low academic performance in Journal of Development and Social Sciences (2023) by Razia (2016), where they describe that students in tuition-based schools face more scholarly pressure than their counterparts in public schools due to foundations, instructors and guardians not giving proper convenient advising. And these students later face problems when they try to apply for a suitable job, but due to the high unemployment rate, they are forced to go abroad for jobs and to pursue their education. The brain drain concept helps to understand why most people are interested in going abroad. The lack of facilities affects the students, who wish to go abroad for further education and creates difficulty for them to develop consistency in their studies.

Discussion

All the following studies agree that academic pressure is the main cause of stress among students. Students have different opinions about stress, different methods to counter stress. Some see this as a source of fuel that ignites the power in them to achieve success regardless of the situation, while others said to lose interest in studies, or were reported to have a hard time studying properly. This is due to the environmental, social or physical factors that affect them. The Journal of Research and Reflections states that brain drain is the cause of stress among teenagers who want to pursue international education so they can leave the country for better opportunities. This contradicts with the Journal of Development and Social Sciences, which states that family tension and fulfilling desires are the cause of stress among students, who want to make their parents proud, yet they are suffering physical and social stress, as well as academic stress. Both are correct, in the sense that they are logical and valid. The Journal of Research and Reflections has failed to address the main issues of students regarding education and the environment they are studying in. It didn't highlight the problems in the education system of Pakistan, which was crucial. The education system is not well-developed and this is from where the concept of brain drain comes in. This is one of the reasons why people want to leave Pakistan.

Conclusion

Overall, Journal of Asian Development Studies and Journal of Development and Social Sciences investigate how social circumstances can affect the behavior of students or teenagers and what they believe is the right way to cure stress and solve mental or physical problems. The Journal of Research and Reflections mainly focuses on the adult population of students, who would like to look for greater opportunities, especially abroad, so this research lacks reliability, as it doesn't mention the teenagers who share the same views or the opposite. The large percentage of teenagers share different views on how they can control stress. Most agree that exams and homeworks can be quite frustrating and complex, but for some they see it as an opportunity to enhance their knowledge skills. Stress can be controlled through various factors, and most students face stress due to low academic performance. It can either come from family pressure or due to unforeseen circumstances that affects their consistency in academics. Lack of facilities and the ongoing situation in the country is another reason for stress that affects the teenagers. Studies suggest that students must develop ways to counter stress, whether it is through extracurricular activities, or attending counselling sessions that help to prevent stress. Each student will have his own opinions of how he or she thinks of stress. They should use the method that suits them best.

AI Use Disclosure

AI-based language tools were used to assist with grammar, organization, and academic formatting. All content, interpretations, and references are based on the author's work and cited sources.

References

- Journal of Research and Reflections in Education: June 2014, Vol.8, No.1, pp 48-54 (<http://www.ue.edu.pk/jrre>)
- Journal of Development and Social Sciences: Jul-Sept 2023, Vol.4, No.3 [967-972] ([http://dx.doi.org/10.47205/jdss.2023\(4-III\)88](http://dx.doi.org/10.47205/jdss.2023(4-III)88))
- Journal of Asian Development Studies: Vol.12, Issue 3 (September 2023)